

Parameter Extraction Method for modeling SiGe HBTs Using Cold Condition S-parameter Measurements

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Abstract—In this work a new parameter extraction method based on the S-parameter measurements of HBTs biased in the cold condition is proposed. The extraction technique gives excellent agreement between the equivalent circuit and the measured S-parameters of a SiGe HBT up to 30GHz.

Index Terms—Heterojunction Bipolar Transistor, Parameter Extraction

I. INTRODUCTION

For circuit design to be reliable, it is necessary to translate the physical behavior of transistors to the simulator properly. This need has resulted in different types of models describing the operation of the transistor, including structural physical models, compact models and equivalent circuit models. Hence, accurate parameter extraction of their constituent parameters is crucial for the development of HBT circuits and applications.

In this sense, the present work focuses on the modeling of SiGe heterojunction bipolar transistor from their small-signal description, adopting an equivalent circuit based on the well-known π -topology, which is popular in commercial circuit simulators such as the Vertical Bipolar Inter-Company Model (VBIC), the Most Exquisite Transistor Model (MEXTRAM) or the High Current Model (HICUM) [1]–[3].

We propose a simple parameter extraction method, with which all model parameters are extracted directly from S-parameter measurements of an HBT polarized in the cold condition. This technique is widely used since the resulting equivalent circuit is simpler than the forward mode one [4], allowing the extraction of HBT parameters with great accuracy without previous knowledge of some geometrical or material parameters, for example, methods like [5], [6], require the knowledge or obtention by non-linear iteration of the built-in potentials and grading coefficients of the capacitive junctions, requirements that may be regarded as a limitation in the development of the extraction methodology.

II. EXPERIMENT

The device under test (DUT) was a common emitter SiGe HBT fabricated on a $0.13\ \mu\text{m}$ BiCMOS process, biased at $V_{BE} = 0$ and $V_{BC} < 0$. On-wafer two-port S-parameter measurements were performed up to 30 GHz using a vector network analyzer (VNA) and ground-signal-ground (GSG) coplanar RF probes. The equipment was previously calibrated up to the probe tips, as shown in Fig. 1, using an SOLT (Short-Open-Line-Through) procedure. The power applied in each port was $-20\ \text{dBm}$ which corresponds to $10\ \mu\text{W}$.

Fig. 1. Test structure pad configuration.

III. PROPOSED METHOD AND RESULTS

Fig. 2 shows the small-signal equivalent circuit of a SiGe HBT in the forward operation mode; in this, R_{bx} , R_e and R_{cx} are the extrinsic resistances associated with the base, emitter and collector regions; C_1 and C_{sub2} represent the remaining parasitic capacitances not removed in the deembedding procedure; C_{bcx} is the extrinsic capacitance associated with the base-collector junction; R_{bk} and C_{bk} are the elements associated with the substrate; R_{bi} , R_{pi} , C_{pi} , C_{bci} and the transconductance gm are the parameters associated with the intrinsic operation of the transistor.

Fig. 2. Small-signal equivalent circuit model for a SiGe HBT.

Under the bias conditions established for the measurement, series resistances R_{bx} and R_{cx} , dynamic resistances R_{π} and R_e as well as the transconductance gm effects can be neglected. Thus, the model can be reduced to the one presented in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Small-signal equivalent circuit model for a SiGe HBT biased at $V_{BE} = 0$ V and $V_{BC} < 0$ V.

In accordance with this circuit, the following admittance parameters can be associated.

$$Y_{11} = j\omega C_1 + j\omega C_{bcx} + \frac{1}{R_{bi} + \frac{1}{j\omega(C_{bci} + C_{\pi})}} \quad (1)$$

$$Y_{12} = Y_{21} = -j\omega C_{bcx} - \frac{j\omega C_{bci}}{1 + j\omega R_{bi}(C_{bci} + C_{\pi})} \quad (2)$$

$$Y_{22} = j\omega C_{bcx} + \frac{j\omega C_{bci}(1 + j\omega R_{bi}C_{\pi})}{1 + j\omega R_{bi}(C_{bci} + C_{\pi})} + j\omega C_{sub2} + \frac{1}{R_{bk} + \frac{1}{j\omega C_{bk}}} \quad (3)$$

Subsequently, the following expression can be obtained from equation (1):

$$\frac{\omega^2}{\text{Re}(Y_{11})} = \omega^2 R_{bi} + \frac{1}{R_{bi}(C_{bci} + C_{\pi})} \quad (4)$$

After performing a linear regression of the experimental $\omega^2/\text{Re}(Y_{11})$ versus ω^2 data, R_{bi} and an equivalent capacitance C_{eq} that considers the C_{bci} and C_{π} effects can be obtained

from the corresponding slope and the intercept with the abscises as shown in Fig 4.

Fig. 4. Linear regression used to determine R_{bi} and C_{eq} .

From equation (2) the expression (5) can be obtained in order to determine the effects of the C_{bci} and C_{π} separately.

$$\frac{\omega^2}{\text{Re}(Y_{12})} = \frac{1}{C_{bci}R_{bi}(C_{bci} + C_{\pi})} + \frac{R_{bi}(C_{bci} + C_{\pi})}{C_{bci}}\omega^2 \quad (5)$$

Thus, as indicated in Fig 5 both capacitive values can be obtained from the linear regression of (5).

Fig. 5. Linear regression used to determine C_{bci} and C_{π} .

Once R_{bi} , C_{bci} and C_π have been determined, the mean value of equation (6) as a function of frequency can be used to assess C_{bcx} , as it is illustrated in Fig 6.

$$\frac{\text{Im}(Y_{11})}{\omega} - \frac{(C_{bci} + C_\pi)}{R_{bi}^2 \omega^2 (C_{bci} + C_\pi)^2} = C_{bcx} \quad (6)$$

Fig. 6. Mean value showing the extracted value for C_{bcx} .

Substituting the extracted values for R_{bi} , C_{bci} , C_π and C_{bcx} to (7), Y_{sub} is obtained. Consequently, R_{bk} and C_{bk} can be obtained from the slope and the intercept after performing a linear regression of the $\omega^2/\text{Re}(Y_{sub})$ versus ω^2 data, as is shown in Fig 7.

$$Y_{sub} = j\omega C_{sub2} + \frac{1}{R_{bk} + \frac{1}{j\omega C_{bk}}} = Y_{22} - j\omega C_{bcx} - \frac{j\omega C_{bci}(1 + j\omega R_{bi} C_\pi)}{1 + j\omega R_{bi}(C_{bci} + C_\pi)} \quad (7)$$

Finally, the capacitances C_{sub2} and C_1 , associated with the passivation layer between interconnection metals and contact layer can be extracted from (8) and (9) respectively

$$C_{sub2} = \frac{\text{Im}(Y_{sub})}{\omega} - \frac{C_{bk}}{1 + C_{bk}^2 R_{bk}^2 \omega^2} \quad (8)$$

$$C_1 = \frac{\text{Im}(Y_{11}) - C_{bcx}}{\omega} - \frac{1}{(C_{bci} + C_\pi) \left(R_{bi}^2 + \frac{1}{C_{eq}^2 \omega^2} \right)} \quad (9)$$

In order to verify the validity of the proposed extraction method, once that all the model parameters associated with the circuit in Fig.3 were determined, equivalent circuit

Fig. 7. Linear regression used to determine R_{bk} and C_{bk}

simulations were carried out to reproduce the HBT admittance parameters, the employed values are summarized in Table I, and the results of these simulations are shown in Fig. 8. Notice the excellent simulation-experiment correlation.

TABLE I
EXTRACTED PARAMETER VALUES

Parameter	Extracted value	Unit
C_1	3.5×10^{-15}	F
R_{bi}	75	Ω
C_{bcx}	2.82×10^{-15}	F
C_π	24×10^{-15}	F
C_{bci}	9.3×10^{-15}	F
C_{bk}	27.6×10^{-15}	F
R_{bk}	105	Ω
C_{sub2}	27×10^{-15}	F

Fig. 8. Comparison between simulated and experimental admittances.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

A simple and accurate parameter extraction methodology, based solely on S-parameter measurements, for the extraction and characterization of the HBT in a cold polarization condition has been presented, obtaining a set of parameter values physically acceptable and an excellent agreement between the measured data and extracted equivalent circuit model, eliminating the need of an optimization procedure, commonly employed for this characterization technique.

Considering that under zero-bias conditions, the base-collector and collector-substrate junctions are reverse biased, which is valid for the common-emitter forward operation mode, the capacitances are considered bias independent, therefore, the extracted values for C_{bcx} , C_{bci} , C_{bk} , R_{bk} , C_{sub2} and C_1 are valid for forward operation of the HBT. On the other hand, the dynamic capacitance and resistance, C_{pi} and R_{bi} , respectively, require a bias dependent interpretation.

When the parasitics of the pad structure are de-embedded, the capacitances associated to the passivation layer between interconnection metals and $n+$ contact layers are not considered, therefore, to obtain a good correlation between experimental data and the simulated model, they should be taken into account in the extraction procedure, in order to incorporate them in the final model.

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